

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PAUL****FIRST NAME: DEBORAH****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-12)
2. Pitfalls with commas and apostrophe (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 17, 19-20)
3. English Language variant (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25-33)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-39)
5. Chicago Manual Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41, 45, 47-48)

LINGUISTIC RESOURCES REQUIRED TO ENHANCE WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

The course ACA-401D provides an opportunity to develop the art of academic and technical writing. This course equips students with the skills required to become proficient writers. ACA-401D allows students to punctuate and use style guides appropriately while acknowledging the work of other scholars. The areas mentioned provide the framework for students to improve their critical thinking skills while writing according to rules and regulations.

Having gone through the contents of this period, one can only acknowledge that the assigned readings would help students to carefully elaborate their thoughts, ideas, and research findings while supporting these findings with pertinent examples. Furthermore, the course would allow students to rigorously reason each pointer while logically sequencing them. These writing skills are necessary not only for academic purposes but also for technical and everyday writing. Based on my review of the course, the skills

outlined in this period will allow students to develop a repertoire of linguistic resources that would improve their writing skills.

The response paper covers five major writing themes. The themes highlight how academic writing achieves precision while establishing authority and credibility. Placing attention on writing style and use of punctuation marks. To support ideas, the author uses an assortment of examples. The response paper will end with conclusions.

2) EXPLORING HOW TO EDIT ACADEMIC ESSAYS

The final stage of the writing process is editing. During editing, authors check for errors and inconsistencies. They also explore opportunities for improving the grammar and layout of ideas. Writers, including myself, tend to dislike this stage of the writing process since it involves meticulously going through the written document to correct spelling, grammar, punctuation, and formatting errors. For this reason, Cleenerck and Gulma recommend that students put away their essays for a period before editing them. I find this advice relatable because I am inclined to edit immediately after completing a writing task.

A student who follows the advice above gets an opportunity to revise systematically, using fresh eyes, the structure and organization of a paper. EUCLID University dictates clear guidelines for structuring essays (introduction, body, followed by conclusion). These guidelines are in keeping with best practices. The university recommends that students consider citation and referencing conventions when planning and organizing essays. Editing ensures that authors comply with their preferred referencing style throughout the document. Through the editing process, authors confirm that punctuation marks are appropriate and under the preferred language variant. Overall, editing improves clarity and organization while ensuring clear connections and coherence between paragraphs.

3) AVOIDING PITFALLS WITH THE COMMAS AND APOSTROPHE

Punctuation marks are the traffic signals of a language since they clarify the meaning of sentences. They provide context and dictate how a writing should be read and understood. In other words, punctuation marks tell readers when to stop, slow down or reroute. There are over thirteen different punctuation marks; however, my experience tells me that commas and apostrophes are the most frequently misunderstood punctuation marks. Personally, commas are not my best friends. My husband often tells me to remember to add the comma. I have found that misusing commas complicates the writing process, and when deployed inappropriately, it changes the meaning of sentences. If utilized incorrectly, the comma connects statements that should not connect and breaks apart sentences that are to be connected.

English Language experts often advise students "to use commas [an individual should be able to identify and] recognize an independent clause, a subject, and a coordinating conjunction" (Lutovich and Chan 2000, 8). Having a firm knowledge of the rules governing the use of commas would help students avoid misusing commas. Comma splicing, random insertion of commas, and missing them all together are three of the most frequently observed errors. Comma splicing involves using a comma to combine two sentences without a conjunction (Karplus 2023, 110). An example of comma splicing is Yesterday I cooked ackee and salt fish for breakfast, [but] today I made cornmeal porridge. Here, the author joins two independent sentences by comma instead of another form of punctuation mark (for example, a full stop). Add a conjunction to continue using the comma in the sentence; for example- Yesterday I cooked ackee and salt fish for breakfast, but today I made cornmeal porridge.

The random utilization of commas is alluring for students who often place them where there is defining information, especially at the beginning of a sentence. However, Cleenewerck and Gulma discourage employing commas in that way (2021, 19). For example, instead of writing her daughter, Mary was her favorite; remove the comma and rewrite the statement as - Her daughter Mary was her favorite. Finally, writers tend to miss commas completely. For that reason, Cleenewerck and Gulma posit that commas should surround a defining clause, after an introductory adverb, and between more than one qualitative adjective (2021, 19).

The temptation is there to use an apostrophe where it does not belong. A common mistake I often make when using the apostrophe involves forgetting its use to make a word possessive. Errors occur when pluralizing a word. It is important to note that the effective use of punctuation marks adds precision and expresses thoughts and ideas clearly.

4) THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE VARIANT

There are different variations to the English Language, each having its nuances — as it relates to style, grammar, pronunciation, and spelling. Two of the most popular variations are from the UK and the US. A comparison of the two variations reveals that the UK variant tends to be less declarative than the US. A Closer examination of the use of grammar and syntax shows that the positioning of modifying phrases differs between the two. Users of the UK variant tend to employ more complicated constructions, while the reverse is true for their US counterparts (The Economist Newspaper 2015, 160). If you are from the English-speaking Caribbean like me, you are more likely to use the UK variation. As such, I would record today's date in the format day first, followed by month, then year. My friend who lives in the US and subscribes to the US language format would record his date by putting month first, followed by day, then year. Though I chose to mention variations in date, a more significant variation lies in the spelling. There are some words that have similar pronunciations but are spelled differently based on the language variant. Take, for example, the word *centre*. Those who subscribe to the UK variation would put the 'r' before the 'e', while those who subscribe to the US variation put the 'e' before the 'r.'

Another consequential variation occurs with the use of punctuation marks. The UK variation uses single quotes (‘’) for initial quotations, while the US style uses double quotes (“”) for initial quotes. There is also a variation in the treatment of quotation marks found within the original reference. The UK variation uses double quotation marks, while the US variation uses a single quote (Penn 2023). It is important to note that the US variation stipulates where full stops and commas appear within the closing quotation marks. As a rule, punctuation marks are positioned inside the quotation mark (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 32). Understanding the difference in language variation is critical since it creates excellent writers who are less inclined to use improper grammar mechanics.

5) PLAGERISM

Quotations and indents are two popular ways in which writers highlight the work of others. Failing to recognize and highlight the work of others results in plagiarism. For this reason, Cleenewerck and Gulma advise that a solution to preventing plagiarism is "to properly CITE the author or sources that have provided the information you are using" (2021, 34). There are diverse ways in which a writer can cite the sources used. These include paraphrasing, utilizing in-text citations, and quotations.

Despite the diverse ways to avoid plagiarism, authors continue to find themselves in situations where they are guilty of intellectual dishonesty. Authors like Zhang contend that knowledge and awareness about ethical considerations, formats, and guidelines often determine the extent of plagiarism. Linked to this, inadequate training in how to recognize the work of others may cause plagiarism. Zhang also noted that culture plays a vital role in how people utilize the work of others. By way of example, she explained that in parts of Asia, where respect for authority is prioritized, plagiarism tends to be accepted. She posits that within that cultural context, students are encouraged to memorize the style of experts in their fields (2016, 7) to advance in their careers. This example provides an opportunity for the discussion of intentional versus unintentional plagiarism. Authors like Eaton posit that padded references can symbolize intentionality (2021, 27). Citing the work of scholars like Howard 2010, McDonald, and Adl 2019, Eaton puts forward the view that underdeveloped writing or citation skills can lead to plagiarism.

6) THE CHICAGO MANUAL STYLE

To avoid plagiarism and enhance editing, authors should be au fait with at least one style guide. Familiarity with style guides ensures consistency in writing. My introduction to the MLA and APA style guides came at the undergraduate level, with an introduction to the Turabian style coming later along the journey. After reflecting on my use of the MLA and APA style guides, I can only conclude that they maintain tone while guiding formatting documents. Style guides allow for coherence and uniformity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41), especially when there is more than one contributing author.

EUCLID University recommends that students utilize the Turabian rules. This style guide allows authors to cite sources in either of two ways. The first involves using numbered endnotes or footnotes corresponding with a full citation on the bibliography page (Purdue OWL, 2017). The second is the author-date system, which uses parenthetical citations to identify the author (The University of Chicago Press, n.d.). In most instances, style guides dictate how to use quotations, where to put page numbers, margins and typeface, use of capitalization, et cetera. This style ensures that quotes exceeding one hundred words are blocked. Style guides allow for efficiency and uniformity in writing.

7) CONCLUSION

It is a fact that even some of the most talented minds struggle when presenting their work clearly and concisely. For this reason, authors should familiarize themselves with one or more citation and style guides. Citation and style guides provide directions on grammar and syntax and on presenting, documenting, and formatting ideas. Knowledge of the rules and regulations governing writing style and citation guides serves to cement the foundation used for editing academic and technical writings. The above linguistic resources enhance students' ability to communicate concisely and in a structured way. They provide road maps for writers to conform to language variations, grammatical conventions, and other conventions that speak to the use of the work of others.

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